

Rapid Review on Requirement Engineering for Agile Software Development: seeking for disruptive techniques

A supplemental report of the rapid review protocol and evaluated studies

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Abstract. This is a complement report of the paper **Rapid Review on Requirement Engineering for Agile Software Development: seeking for disruptive techniques**. Here someone can find the complete Rapid Review Protocol and studies have accessed in the paper original.

Keywords: Rapid Review · Requirement Engineering (RE) · Agile Software Development (ASD) · Design Thinking · Artificial Intelligence · User-Centered Design · Disruptive Solution · Agile Development Challenges

1 Planning

To achieve the main goal of this work, we have opted to use the Rapid Review protocol. We based our protocol in the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) protocol elaborated by Kitchenham and Charters [113] with a slight change. Instead of initiating another complete review from scratch, we focused on secondary and tertiary studies that already cataloged or analyzed these tools, techniques, and RE phases.

Requirements Engineering (RE) is the basis of the software engineering process. Due to its importance, many studies have been carried out to identify RE techniques and tools for Agile Software Development (ASD). Many studies have been done to consolidate the primary studies, but each one has a different focus. Therefore, a full understanding of ER for ASD is required.

The main goal is to identify which phases, techniques, and tools academia and industry use for Requirements Engineering for Agile Software Development.

As secondary objectives:

1. Identify disruptive techniques and tools used in Requirements Engineering (RE) for Agile Software Development (ASD);

2. Identify and catalog the challenges faced by using disruptive techniques and tools in RE for ASD according to the founded papers

PICOC

- **Population:** Developers, researchers, practitioners
- **Intervention:** Disruptive techniques and tools in Requirement Engineering in Agile Software Development
- **Comparison:** Conventional techniques and tools in Requirement Engineering
- **Outcome:** Identify disruptive techniques and tools used in Requirements Engineering (RE) for Agile Software Development (ASD). Identify and catalog the challenges faced by using disruptive techniques
- **Context:** Academia and industry of software development

Research Questions

- RQ.1 What phases, techniques, and tools of Requirement Engineering have been used by literature and industry for Agile Software Development?
- RQ.2 What disruptive techniques and tools used in Requirements Engineering for Agile Software Development have been identified?
- RQ.3 According to the founded studies, what challenges the disruptive techniques and tools in Requirement Engineering for Agile Software Development have been faced?

Table 1. Keywords and Synonyms

Keyword	Synonyms
Agile Software Development	ASD, Agile Development, Agile Methods, Agile Techniques
Requirement Engineering	RE, Requirement Gathering, Requirement Analysis, Requirement Documentation, Requirement Elicitation, Requirement Management, Requirement Specification, Requirement Validation, Requirement Verification

Keywords and Synonyms

Search String TITLE-ABS-KEY(("Agile Software Development" OR "Agile Development" OR "Agile Methods" OR "Agile Techniques") AND ("Requirement Gathering" OR "Requirement Engineering" OR "Requirement Analysis" OR "Requirement Documentation" OR "Requirement Elicitation" OR "Requirement Management" OR "Requirement Specification" OR "Requirement Validation" OR "Requirement Verification")) AND (TITLE("Map") OR TITLE("Review") OR TITLE("Study") OR TITLE("Studies") OR TITLE("Survey") AND (PUBYEAR \geq 2015).

Digital Databases

- ACM Digital Library (<http://portal.acm.org>)
- El Compendex (<http://www.engineeringvillage.com>)
- IEEE Digital Library (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>)
- ISI Web of Science (<http://www.isiknowledge.com>)
- Science@Direct (<http://www.sciencedirect.com>)
- Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com>)
- Springer Link (<http://link.springer.com>)

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- Literature and industry studies
- Peer-reviewed studies
- Studies available online
- Studies published up to and including 2015
- Studies written in English;

Exclusion Criteria

- Duplicated studies
- Grey literature
- Studies not focused on RE and ASD
- Studies published before 2015
- The study is not secondary or tertiary research.

Data Extraction Form For the study:

- Researchers (Analyst / Reviewer) and overall notes
- Which disruptive solutions does the study present?
- Which traditional solutions does the study present?

For each solution found in the study, the following fields were assessed:

- Domain
- Type of solution
- Phases of Requirement Engineering
- Describe the challenges, if any, presented in the study
- Type of contribution
- Describe the contribution of the studies.
- Which research question does the study address?
- Which objective does the study address?

2 Conducting

2.1 Digital Libraries Search Strings

For each digital library, adjustments were needed in the query to suit each search tool.

ACM Digital Library

<https://dl-acm-org.ez54.periodicos.capes.gov.br/action/doSearch?fillQuickSearch=false&target=advanced&expand=dl&AfterMonth=1&AfterYear=2015&BeforeMonth=12&BeforeYear=2021&AllField=AllField%3A%28%28+%22Agile+Software+Development%22+OR+%22Agile+Development%22+OR+%22Agile+Methods%22+OR+%22Agile+Techniques%22+%29+AND+%28+%22Requirement+Engineering%22+OR+%22Requirement+Analysis%22+OR+%22Requirement+Documentation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Elicitation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Management%22+OR+%22Requirement+Specification%22+OR+%22Requirement+Validation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Verification%22+%29%29+AND+Title%3A%28MAP+OR+Review%29>

IEEE Digital Library

(“All Metadata”:“Agile Software Development” OR “All Metadata”:“Agile Development” OR “All Metadata”:“Agile Methods” OR “All Metadata”:“Agile Techniques”) AND (“All Metadata”:“Requirement Engineering” OR “All Metadata”:“Requirement Analysis” OR “All Metadata”:“Requirement Documentation” OR “All Metadata”:“Requirement Elicitation” OR “All Metadata”:“Requirement Management” OR “All Metadata”:“Requirement Specification” OR “All Metadata”:“Requirement Validation” OR “All Metadata”:“Requirement Verification”)

AND

(“Document Title”:“MAP” OR “Document Title”:“Review” OR “Document Title”:Survey)

ISI Web of Science: TS=((“Agile Software Development” OR “Agile Development” OR “Agile Methods” OR “Agile Techniques”) AND (“Requirement Engineering” OR “Requirement Analysis” OR “Requirement Documentation” OR “Requirement Elicitation” OR “Requirement Management” OR “Requirement Specification” OR “Requirement Validation” OR “Requirement Verification”)) AND ((TI=(Map)) OR (TI=(Review)))

Obs.: When searching, manually fill in the fields ‘Publication date (from-to)’

Science@Direct

(“Agile Software Development” OR “Agile Development” OR “Agile Methods” OR “Agile Techniques”) AND (“Requirement Engineering” OR “Requirement Analysis” OR “Requirement Documentation” OR “Requirement Elicitation” OR “Requirement Management”)

(“Agile Software Development” OR “Agile Development” OR “Agile Methods” OR “Agile Techniques”) AND (“Requirement Specification” OR “Requirement Validation” OR “Requirement Verification”)

Obs.: The query had to be separated due to the limitation of the tool’s Boolean operators. Both queries above used the title field to filter “MAP OR Review” and the year field for the years 2015-2021.

Springer Link

<https://link-springer-com.ez54.periodicos.capes.gov.br/search?dc.title=Review&showAll=true&query=%28%28%22Agile+Software+Development%22+OR+%22Agile+Development%22+OR+%22Agile+Methods%22+OR+%22Agile+Techniques%22+%29+AND+%28%22Requirement+Engineering%22+OR+%22Requirement+Analysis%22+OR+%22Requirement+Documentation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Elicitation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Management%22+OR+%22Requirement+Specification%22+OR+%22Requirement+Validation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Verification%22+%29%29&date-facet-mode=between&facet-start-year=2015&previous-start-year=2005&facet-end-year=2021&previous-end-year=2022>

<https://link-springer-com.ez54.periodicos.capes.gov.br/search?dc.title=MAP&showAll=true&query=%28%28%22Agile+Software+Development%22+OR+%22Agile+Development%22+OR+%22Agile+Methods%22+OR+%22Agile+Techniques%22+%29+AND+%28%22Requirement+Engineering%22+OR+%22Requirement+Analysis%22+OR+%22Requirement+Documentation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Elicitation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Management%22+OR+%22Requirement+Specification%22+OR+%22Requirement+Validation%22+OR+%22Requirement+Verification%22+%29%29&date-facet-mode=between&facet-start-year=2015&previous-start-year=2005&facet-end-year=2021&previous-end-year=2022>

Obs.: Two links had to be used. One for the search with the word ‘MAP’ in the title and the other for the word ‘Review’.

2.2 Conducting Overview

Figure 1 depicts the process for carrying out the Quick Review.

3 Data

Table 2. Rapid review selected studies

ID	Author [ref] (key) digital database	Year Pub.	Phases of RE	Type of Solutions	Quantities		
					Solutions		Challenges
					Disruptive	Trad.	
S1	Heikkila et al. [86] (9) El Compendex	2015	All	All	1	14	3
S2	Mognon et al. [140] (169) Springer Link	2017	1	Te	0	1	0
S3	Heck and Zaidman [84] (41) Springer Link	2018			0	3	0
S4	Lim et al. [120] (105) Springer Link	2021	1	F	0	1	0
S5	Albuquerque et al. [6] (107) ACM Digital Library	2020	1;5	Po	1	10	8
S6	Ainhoa et al. [10] (159) Science@Direct	2019	1	Me;Po;Te	5	0	3
S7	Hafidz and Sensuse [80] (29) El Compendex	2019	5	A;F;To	0	3	0
S8	Zamudio et al. [223] (11) El Compendex	2017	All	Te	0	14	3
S9	Fernandez-Diego et al. [69] (75) El Compendex	2020	5	Me	32	9	0
S10	Raharjana et al. [167] (235) El Compendex	2021	1	Te	19	0	11
S11	Medeiros et al. [136] (191) El Compendex	2015	1	Te	1	26	49
S12	Alfraihi and Lano [12] (225) El Compendex	2017	All	A	0	1	3
S13	Settelen et al. [188] (151) El Compendex	2020	All	F	0	1	0
S14	Villamizar et al. [212] (45) El Compendex	2018	1	A;F;G;To	0	8	1
S15	Amin et al. [22] (24) Springer Link	2018			0	0	0
S16	Satria et al. [182] (32) El Compendex	2017	All	A;F;Me;To	3	2	0
S17	Irum et al. [93] (34) Science@Direct	2015	All	A;Pa	0	16	6
S18	Jarzębowicz and Weichbroth [104] (40) Springer Link	2021	1;4	Pa	0	4	1
S19	Jayatilleke and Lai [105] (48) El Compendex	2018	1;5	Pa	0	3	3
S20	Zorzetti et al. [226] (54) Springer Link	2021	All	A;Me	2	0	0
S21	Younas et al. [221] (58) El Compendex	2018	All	Me	1	0	5
S22	Wijaya et al. [216] (62) El Compendex	2018	All	A	0	1	5
S23	Schön et al. [184] (70) Scopus	2017	All	A;Me;Pa	5	19	6
S24	Villamizar et al. [210] (72) El Compendex	2019	All	A	0	1	2
S25	Tsilionis et al. [206] (98) El Compendex	2021	1;4	Pa	0	2	0
S26	Yaman et al. [220] (104) Springer Link	2016	All	A;Pa;Po	3	2	3
S27	Moramontes et al. [138] (120) Springer Link	2016			0	0	0
S28	Hasnain et al. [83] (124) Springer Link	2021	1;4	Pa	2	4	3
S29	Caballero et al. [39] (132) El Compendex	2016	All	A;Pa	5	8	0
S30	Magare et al. [129] (138) El Compendex	2021	All	A;Pa	6	0	0
S31	Perkusich et al. [161] (146) Scopus	2020	All	Me;Pa;Po	6	0	2
S32	Behutiye et al. [29] (164) El Compendex	2020			0	0	0
S33	Ijaz et al. [91] (172) El Compendex	2019	5	Me	3	0	0
S34	Alsaqaf et al. [19] (186) Springer Link	2017	All	A;Pa	1	12	1
S35	Coutinho et al. [50] (190) El Compendex	2019	All	A;Me;Pa	4	1	10
S36	Curcio et al. [51] (192) El Compendex	2018	All	A	1	0	9
S37	Elghariani and Kama [62] (196) El Compendex	2016	All	Pa	1	15	7
S38	Da Silva et al. [194] (204) Springer Link	2016			0	0	0
S39	Riisom et al. [170] (206) El Compendex	2018			0	0	0
S40	Ghozali et al. [77] (216) Science@Direct	2019	5	Pa	4	4	5
S41	Ruiz and Salantri [173] (232) Springer Link	2019			0	0	0
S42	Jarzębowicz and Weichbroth [103] (243) Manual	2021	1	Te	0	14	0
Total					106	199	

1: Elicitation; 2: analysis and Negotiation; 3: Documentation; 4: Verification and Validation; 5: Management
 A: Approach; F: Framework; G: Guidelines; Me: Methods; Mo: Model; Pa: Practice; Po: Process; Te: Technique; To: Tool

Table 3: All selected studies

Key	Ref	Title	Year Pub.	Source	Status
1	[86]	A clustering-based approach for virtual network function mapping and assigning	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
2	[61]	A cognitive map integrated intuitionistic fuzzy decision-making procedure for provider selection in project management	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
3	[142]	A Comparative Review on the Agile Tenets in the IT Service Management and the Software Engineering Domains	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
4	[144]	A feature location approach for mapping application features extracted from crowd-based screencasts to source code	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
5	[159]	A literature review on story test driven development	2010	El Compendex	Rejected
6	[94]	A mapping study on knowledge management in agile software development	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
7	[208]	A Mapping Study on Product Owners in Industry: Identifying Future Research Directions	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
8	[208]	A mapping study on product owners in industry: Identifying future research directions	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
9	[86]	A Mapping Study on Requirements Engineering in Agile Software Development	2015	El Compendex	Accepted
10	[28]	A Novel Approach for Improving Security in Software Development in Small Software Firms: A Literature Review	2021	Springer Link	Rejected
11	[224]	A requirements engineering techniques review in agile software development methods	2017	El Compendex	Accepted
12	[222]	A requirements engineering techniques review in agile software development methods	2017	Scopus	Rejected
13	[223]	A Requirements Engineering Techniques Review in Agile Software Development Methods	2017	Springer Link	Rejected
14	[175]	A review of aerodynamic studies on dragonfly flight	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
15	[121]	A Review of Biological Fluid Power Systems and Their Potential Bionic Applications	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
16	[49]	A review of Lean-Kanban approaches in the software development	2013	El Compendex	Rejected
17	[64]	A review of recent programs and future plans for rotorcraft in-flight simulation at Ames Research Center	1991	El Compendex	Rejected
18	[123]	A Review of Redundant Parallel Kinematic Mechanisms	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
19	[33]	A Review of Software Cost Estimation in Agile Software Development Using Soft Computing Techniques	2016	El Compendex	Rejected
20	[150]	A Review of Use Case-Based Development Effort Estimation Methods in the System Development Context	2019	Springer Link	Rejected
21	[143]	A review on preparative and semi-preparative offgel electrophoresis for multidimensional protein/peptide assessment	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
22	[7]	A Review on the Critical Success Factors of Agile Software Development	2017	Springer Link	Rejected
23	[190]	A roadmap for software engineering for the cloud: Results of a systematic review	2013	El Compendex	Rejected
24	[22]	A Snapshot of 26 Years of Research on Creativity in Software Engineering - A Systematic Literature Review	2018	Springer Link	Accepted
25	[151]	A Systematic Investigation into the Use of Game Elements in the Context of Software Business Landscapes: A Systematic Literature Review	2017	Springer Link	Rejected
26	[43]	A Systematic Literature Review for Service-Oriented Architecture and Agile Development	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
27	[176]	A Systematic Literature Review of Challenges and Critical Success Factors in Agile Requirement Engineering	2018	ISI Web of Science	Rejected
28	[4]	A Systematic Literature Review of Improved Knowledge Management in Agile Software Development	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
29	[80]	A systematic literature review of improved knowledge management in agile software development	2019	El Compendex	Accepted
30	[26]	A Systematic Literature Review of Machine Learning Estimation Approaches in Scrum Projects	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
31	[44]	A systematic literature review of modern software visualization	2020	Springer Link	Rejected
32	[182]	A systematic literature review of the improved agile software development	2017	El Compendex	Accepted
33	[93]	A systematic literature review on agile requirements engineering practices and challenges	2015	El Compendex	Rejected
34	[93]	A systematic literature review on agile requirements engineering practices and challenges	2015	Science@Direct	Accepted
35	[20]	A systematic literature review on factors impacting agile adaptation in global software development	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
36	[20]	A Systematic Literature Review on Factors Impacting Agile Adaptation in Global Software Development	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
37	[97]	A Systematic Literature Review on Global Software Development Life Cycle	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
38	[102]	A Systematic Literature Review on Implementing Non-functional Requirements in Agile Software Development: Issues and Facilitating Practices	2021	Scopus	Rejected
39	[101]	A Systematic Literature Review on Implementing Non-functional Requirements in Agile Software Development: Issues and Facilitating Practices	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
40	[104]	A Systematic Literature Review on Implementing Non-functional Requirements in Agile Software Development: Issues and Facilitating Practices	2021	Springer Link	Accepted
41	[84]	A systematic literature review on quality criteria for agile requirements specifications	2018	Springer Link	Accepted
42	[128]	A systematic literature review on the application of multicriteria decision making methods for information security risk assessment	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
43	[133]	A systematic mapping study on practical approaches to teaching software engineering	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
44	[218]	A Systematic Mapping Study on Requirements Scoping	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
45	[212]	A systematic mapping study on security in agile requirements engineering	2018	El Compendex	Accepted
46	[24]	A Systematic Review and Analytical Evaluation of Security Requirements Engineering Approaches	2019	Springer Link	Rejected
47	[137]	A systematic review of additive manufacturing education: Towards engineering education research in AM	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
48	[105]	A systematic review of requirements change management	2018	El Compendex	Accepted
49	[34]	A systematic review on software cost estimation in Agile Software Development	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
50	[180]	A systematic review on the engineering of software for ubiquitous systems	2016	El Compendex	Rejected
51	[192]	A systematic review on the use of Definition of Done on agile software development projects	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
52	[192]	A Systematic Review on the Use of Definition of Done on Agile Software Development Projects	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
53	[42]	Acceptance of agile methodologies: A critical review and conceptual framework	2009	El Compendex	Rejected
54	[226]	Adopting Agile Software Development Combined with User-Centered Design and Lean Startup: A Systematic Literature Review on Maturity Models	2021	Springer Link	Accepted
55	[66]	Adopting Scrum as an Agile approach in distributed software development: A review of literature	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
56	[209]	Agile adoption issues in large scale organizations: A review	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
57	[152]	Agile Development in Bureaucratic Environments: A Literature Review	2019	Springer Link	Rejected
58	[221]	Agile development in the cloud computing environment: A systematic review	2018	El Compendex	Accepted
59	[87]	Agile interaction design and test-driven development of user interfaces - A literature review	2010	El Compendex	Rejected
60	[178]	Agile Methodologies in Education: A Review	2019	Springer Link	Rejected

Key	Ref	Title	Year Pub.	Source	Status
61	[3]	Agile Methods and Cyber-Physical Systems Development—A Review with Preliminary Analysis	2020	Springer Link	Rejected
62	[216]	Agile Methods for ERP Implementation: A Systematic Literature Review	2018	El Compendex	Accepted
63	[40]	Agile methods tailoring - A systematic literature review	2015	El Compendex	Rejected
64	[157]	Agile practices adoption in CMMI organizations: A systematic literature review	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
65	[98]	Agile practices in global software engineering - A systematic map	2010	El Compendex	Rejected
66	[56]	Agile product line engineering - A systematic literature review	2011	El Compendex	Rejected
67	[168]	Agile Project Management Challenges and Mapping Solutions: A Systematic Literature Review	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
68	[184]	Agile Requirements Engineering: A systematic literature review	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
69	[185]	Agile Requirements Engineering: A systematic literature review	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
70	[184]	Agile Requirements Engineering: A systematic literature review	2017	Scopus	Accepted
71	[134]	AH-CID: A tool to automatically detect human-centric issues in app reviews	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
72	[210]	An approach for reviewing security-related aspects in agile requirements specifications of web applications	2019	El Compendex	Accepted
73	[211]	An efficient approach for reviewing security-related aspects in agile requirements specifications of web applications	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
74	[146]	An international review of energy models: Introduction of a new paradigm	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
75	[69]	An update on effort estimation in agile software development: A systematic literature review	2020	El Compendex	Accepted
76	[5]	Analysis of the implementation of VDC from a lean perspective: Literature review	2013	El Compendex	Rejected
77	[171]	Application of agile methods in embedded systems development: A systematic review	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
78	[25]	Aspects of software quality applied to the process of agile software development: a systematic literature review	2019	Springer Link	Rejected
79	[25]	Aspects of software quality applied to the process of agile software development: a systematic literature review	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
80	[57]	Assembly lines of the future: A literature review of research articles from 2000-2014	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
81	[111]	Assessing the maturity of a research area: bibliometric review and proposed framework	2016	Springer Link	Rejected
82	[95]	Automatic Mapping between Real Hardware Composition and ROADM Model for Agile Node Updates	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
83	[2]	Bayesian networks for enhancement of requirements engineering: a literature review	2016	Springer Link	Rejected
84	[122]	BizDevOps: A Multivocal Literature Review	2020	Springer Link	Rejected
85	[217]	Business Modeling and Flexibility in Software-Intensive Product Development - A Systematic Literature Review	2018	Springer Link	Rejected
86	[158]	Business to system requirements agile mapping	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
87	[201]	Capability mapping to improve manufacturing network performance: how a factory can target growth	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
88	[46]	Challenges and Recommendations for the Design and Conduct of Global Software Engineering Courses: A Systematic Review	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
89	[71]	Challenges in agile software development: A systematic literature review	2016	El Compendex	Rejected
90	[68]	Challenges in Combining Agile Development and CMMI: A Systematic Literature Review	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
91	[68]	Challenges in Combining Agile Development and CMMI: A Systematic Literature Review	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
92	[31]	Challenges in the selection, design and implementation of an online submission and peer review system for STM journals	2007	El Compendex	Rejected
93	[79]	Challenges of using software size in agile software development: A systematic literature review	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
94	[179]	Characterizing DevOps Culture: A Systematic Literature Review BT - Software Process Improvement and Capability Determination	2018	Springer Link	Rejected
95	[78]	CHARM: Adopting Digitalization in Community Health Assessment and Review on Mobile	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
96	[189]	Collaborating on mobile app design through pair programming: A practice-oriented approach overview and expert review	2015	El Compendex	Rejected
97	[112]	Comparison between traditional plan-based and agile software processes according to team size & project domain (A systematic literature review)	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
98	[206]	Conceptual Modeling Versus User Story Mapping: Which is the Best Approach to Agile Requirements Engineering?	2021	El Compendex	Accepted
99	[54]	Continuous Development and Testing of Access and Usage Control: A Systematic Literature Review	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
100	[106]	Correlation mapping: Rapid method for retrieving microcirculation morphology from optical coherence tomography intensity images	2011	El Compendex	Rejected
101	[9]	Creative techniques for requirements elicitation in agile development: A systematic review of the literature	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
102	[165]	Crossing the chasm: a 'tube-map' for agent-based social simulation of policy scenarios in spatially-distributed systems	2019	Springer Link	Rejected
103	[65]	Customer Feedback and Data Collection Techniques in Software R&D: A Literature Review BT - Software Business	2015	Springer Link	Rejected
104	[220]	Customer Involvement in Continuous Deployment: A Systematic Literature Review BT - Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality	2016	Springer Link	Accepted
105	[120]	Data-Driven Requirements Elicitation: A Systematic Literature Review	2021	Springer Link	Accepted
106	[6]	Defining agile requirements change management: A mapping study	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
107	[6]	Defining Agile Requirements Change Management: A Mapping Study	2020	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
108	[196]	Developing a social collaborative platform for a curriculum review process: A case study of an iterative component based method	2009	El Compendex	Rejected
109	[215]	Developing intellectual capital within agile it teams: A literature review	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
110	[118]	DevOps in an ISO 13485 regulated environment: A multivocal literature review	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
111	[118]	DevOps in an ISO 13485 Regulated Environment: A Multivocal Literature Review	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
112	[88]	Digital-physical product development: A review and research agenda	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
113	[52]	Distributed pair programming: A systematic literature review	2015	El Compendex	Rejected
114	[156]	Dynamic maps for future navigation systems: Agile design exploration of user interface concepts	2009	El Compendex	Rejected
115	[183]	ECSS evolution - Project phasing and reviews in future space projects	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
116	[1]	Educational trends in software engineering: A systematic review study	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
117	[148]	Efficiency enhancement in CNC industry using value stream mapping, work standardization and line balancing	2016	El Compendex	Rejected
118	[96]	Empirical evidence on the link between object-oriented measures and external quality attributes: a systematic literature review	2015	Springer Link	Rejected
119	[205]	Essential Approaches to Dual-Track Agile: Results from a Grey Literature Review BT - Software Business	2021	Springer Link	Rejected
120	[138]	Establishing the State of the Art of Frameworks, Methods and Methodologies Focused on Lightning Software Process: A Systematic Literature Review	2016	Springer Link	Accepted
121	[214]	Experimental evaluation of conceptual modelling through mind maps and model driven engineering	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
122	[41]	Factors limiting industrial adoption of test driven development: A systematic review	2011	El Compendex	Rejected
123	[114]	Field Ladar Demonstration (HI-CLASS) program: a review of the phase 2 testing effort	1997	El Compendex	Rejected

Key	Ref	Title	Year Pub.	Source	Status
124	[83]	Functional Requirement-Based Test Case Prioritization in Regression Testing: A Systematic Literature Review	2021	Springer Link	Accepted
125	[11]	Game development software engineering process life cycle: a systematic review	2016	Springer Link	Rejected
126	[125]	Gamification for Improving Software Project Management Processes: A Systematic Literature Review	2019	Springer Link	Rejected
127	[197]	Global software development using agile methodologies: A review of literature	2012	El Compendex	Rejected
128	[99]	Global software engineering and agile practices: A systematic review	2012	El Compendex	Rejected
129	[169]	Ground vehicle route planning in OneSAF using the Battlespace Terrain Reasoning and Analysis Commercial Joint Mapping Toolkit Extensions (BCE)	2009	El Compendex	Rejected
130	[30]	Group decision support systems: A review of industrial applications	1996	El Compendex	Rejected
131	[60]	High speed VNIR/SWIR HSI sensor for vegetation trait mapping	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
132	[39]	How Agile Developers Integrate User-Centered Design into Their Processes: A Literature Review	2016	El Compendex	Accepted
133	[48]	Identification of Skills for the Formation of Agile High Performance Teams: A Systematic Mapping	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
134	[119]	Identifying the constructs and agile capabilities of data governance and data management: A review of the literature	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
135	[14]	Incremental Development of Safety Cases: A Mapping Study	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
136	[202]	Industry 4.0 impact on Lean Manufacturing: Literature Review	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
137	[115]	Information Requirements for Big Data Projects: A Review of State-of-the-Art Approaches	2018	Springer Link	Rejected
138	[129]	Inherent Mapping Analysis of Agile Development Methodology Through Design Thinking	2021	El Compendex	Accepted
139	[107]	Integrating ERP to accelerate business process agility: A case study and critical research review in Indian pharmaceutical industry	2012	El Compendex	Rejected
140	[45]	Integrating the environmental and social sustainability pillars into the lean and agile supply chain management paradigms: A literature review and future research directions	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
141	[225]	Integration of Usability and Agile Methodologies: A Systematic Review	2015	Springer Link	Rejected
142	[15]	Integration of User Experience and Agile Techniques for Requirements Analysis: A Systematic Review	2021	Scopus	Rejected
143	[16]	Integration of User Experience and Agile Techniques for Requirements Analysis: A Systematic Review	2021	Springer Link	Rejected
144	[161]	Intelligent software engineering in the context of agile software development: A systematic literature review	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
145	[161]	Intelligent software engineering in the context of agile software development: A systematic literature review	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
146	[161]	Intelligent software engineering in the context of agile software development: A systematic literature review	2020	Scopus	Accepted
147	[76]	Investigating gaps on Agile Improvement Solutions and their successful adoption in industry projects-A systematic literature review	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
148	[199]	Investigating the impact of peer code review and pair programming on test-driven development	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
149	[155]	Investigation of Agile Mindset Elements by Using Literature Review for a Better Understanding of Agility	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
150	[110]	Investigation on test effort estimation of mobile applications: Systematic literature review and survey	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
151	[188]	Is the 'Job Map' the Next-Generation 'Story Map'? Investigating the Application of Jobs-to-be-Done for Requirements Engineering in Agile Projects	2020	El Compendex	Accepted
152	[162]	IT in lean-based manufacturing industries: Systematic literature review and research issues	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
153	[58]	Journey towards agility - A retro- And prospective review	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
154	[126]	Knowledge Management Diagnostics in Software Development Organizations: A Systematic Literature Review	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
155	[181]	Knowledge sharing via social media in software development: a systematic literature review	2017	Springer Link	Rejected
156	[32]	Lean management and product innovation: A critical review	2015	El Compendex	Rejected
157	[139]	Lean strategy map construction with performance indicators of the balanced scorecard	2013	El Compendex	Rejected
158	[131]	Leeway of Lean Concept to Optimize Big Data in Manufacturing Industry: An Exploratory Review	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
159	[10]	Leveraging creativity in requirements elicitation within agile software development: A systematic literature review	2019	Science@Direct	Accepted
160	[8]	Leveraging creativity in requirements elicitation within agile software development: A systematic literature review	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
161	[8]	Leveraging creativity in requirements elicitation within agile software development: A systematic literature review	2019	Scopus	Rejected
162	[213]	Life cycle assessment integrated value stream mapping framework to ensure sustainable manufacturing: A case study	2016	El Compendex	Rejected
163	[166]	Locomotion Strategies for Amphibious Robots-A Review	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
164	[29]	Management of quality requirements in agile and rapid software development: A systematic mapping study	2020	El Compendex	Accepted
165	[198]	Mapping participatory design methods to the cognitive process of creativity to facilitate requirements engineering	2012	El Compendex	Rejected
166	[219]	Mapping scrum method building elements to CMMI level 2 requirements	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
167	[23]	Mapping social network to software architecture to detect structure clashes in agile software development	2007	El Compendex	Rejected
168	[130]	Mind-mapping: An effective technique to facilitate requirements engineering in agile software development	2011	El Compendex	Rejected
169	[140]	Modeling in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review	2017	Springer Link	Accepted
170	[132]	Multiple value stream mapping: How to implement work load control in complex systems	2013	El Compendex	Rejected
171	[82]	Non-functional Requirements Engineering Questionnaire: Novel Visions and Review of Literature	2021	Springer Link	Rejected
172	[91]	Non-functional Requirements Prioritization: A Systematic Literature Review	2019	El Compendex	Accepted
173	[36]	NPV approach to material requirements planning theorya 50-year review of these research achievements	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
174	[117]	On dynamic mapping and scheduling of service function chains in SDN/NFV-enabled networks	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
175	[89]	On the Agile Literature Review Approach for Practising Managers: A Proposal	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
176	[195]	Ordering the product backlog in agile software development projects: A systematic literature review	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
177	[195]	Ordering the product backlog in agile software development projects: A systematic literature review	2017	Scopus	Rejected
178	[174]	Organizational Maturity Models Architectures: A Systematic Literature Review BT - Trends and Applications in Software Engineering	2017	Springer Link	Rejected
179	[81]	Popular agile approaches in software development: Review and analysis	2013	El Compendex	Rejected
180	[186]	Probabilistic -Analysis Using Mapped Uncertainties	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
181	[149]	Process Mining and Value Stream Mapping: An Incremental Approach	2021	El Compendex	Rejected
182	[204]	Product Roadmap Alignment - Achieving the Vision Together: A Grey Literature Review	2020	Springer Link	Rejected
183	[75]	Quality assurance in agile software development: A systematic review	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
184	[18]	Quality requirements in large-scale distributed agile projects - A systematic literature review	2017	Scopus	Rejected
185	[18]	Quality requirements in large-scale distributed agile projects - A systematic literature review	2017	El Compendex	Rejected

Key	Ref	Title	Year Pub.	Source	Status
186	[19]	Quality Requirements in Large-Scale Distributed Agile Projects – A Systematic Literature Review	2017	Springer Link	Accepted
187	[55]	Real-time simultaneous localisation and mapping with a single camera	2003	El Compendex	Rejected
188	[124]	Relationship of devops to agile, lean and continuous deployment: A multivocal literature review study	2016	El Compendex	Rejected
189	[74]	Requirements elicitation in agile methodologies: A systematic mapping of literature	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
190	[50]	Requirements engineering and software testing in agile methodologies: A systematic mapping	2019	El Compendex	Accepted
191	[136]	Requirements engineering in agile projects: A systematic mapping based in evidences of industry	2015	El Compendex	Accepted
192	[51]	Requirements engineering: A systematic mapping study in agile software development	2018	El Compendex	Accepted
193	[191]	Review of Current Software Estimation Techniques	2018	Springer Link	Rejected
194	[141]	Review of fatigue monitoring of agile military aircraft	2000	El Compendex	Rejected
195	[35]	Review of formal agile methods as cost-effective airworthiness certification processes	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
196	[62]	Review on Agile requirements engineering challenges	2016	El Compendex	Accepted
197	[116]	Search. Review. Repeat? An empirical study of threats to replicating SLR searches	2020	Springer Link	Rejected
198	[145]	Security Compliance in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Mapping Study	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
199	[90]	Self-organizing maps for agile requirements prioritization	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
200	[100]	Service oriented architecture support in various architecture frameworks: A brief review	2012	El Compendex	Rejected
201	[153]	Software Development Processes for Games: A Systematic Literature Review	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
202	[127]	Software Engineering Analytics—The Need of Post COVID-19 Business: An Academic Review	2021	Springer Link	Rejected
203	[53]	Software Engineering in Medical Informatics: A Systematic Literature Review	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
204	[194]	Software Process Improvement in Small and Medium Enterprises: A Systematic Literature Review	2016	Springer Link	Accepted
205	[193]	Software processes used in university, government, and industry: A systematic review	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
206	[170]	Software security in agile software development: A literature review of challenges and solutions	2018	El Compendex	Accepted
207	[38]	Streamlining semantics from requirements to implementation through agile mind mapping methods	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
208	[63]	Subject-Oriented Value-Stream Mapping with SiSi	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
209	[21]	Supply chain agility in manufacturing companies: A literature review	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
210	[27]	Supply chain performance measurement: A literature review	2010	El Compendex	Rejected
211	[13]	Survey on Differences of Requirements Engineering for Traditional and Agile Development Processes	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
212	[37]	Sustainable value stream mapping (Sus-VSM) in different manufacturing system configurations: Application case studies	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
213	[67]	Sustainable Value Stream Mapping (Sus-VSM): Methodology to visualize and assess manufacturing sustainability performance	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
214	[177]	Systematic literature review of the risk management process literature for the public sector	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
215	[77]	Systematic literature review on decision-making of requirement engineering from agile software development	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
216	[77]	Systematic Literature Review on Decision-Making of Requirement Engineering from Agile Software Development	2019	Science@Direct	Accepted
217	[77]	Systematic Literature Review on Decision-Making of Requirement Engineering from Agile Software Development	2019	ISI Web of Science	Rejected
218	[77]	Systematic Literature Review on Decision-Making of Requirement Engineering from Agile Software Development	2019	Scopus	Rejected
219	[164]	Systematic Literature Review on Global Software Development Risks in Agile Methodology	2020	El Compendex	Rejected
220	[108]	Systematic literature review on the impacts of agile release engineering practices	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
221	[109]	Systematic literature review on the impacts of agile release engineering practices	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
222	[147]	Systematic review of web application security development model	2015	Springer Link	Rejected
223	[85]	Technical reviews in agile development: Case mobile-D	2006	El Compendex	Rejected
224	[92]	The Implementation Lean and Green Manufacturing through Sustainable Value Stream Mapping	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
225	[12]	The integration of agile development and model driven development: A systematic literature review	2017	El Compendex	Accepted
226	[70]	The need for CD mapping standards to enhance sustainability, agility and profitability	2014	El Compendex	Rejected
227	[59]	The quest for productivity in software engineering: A practitioners systematic literature review	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
228	[207]	Threat analysis of software systems: A systematic literature review	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
229	[200]	Towards an agile IT organisation: A review of prior literature	2008	El Compendex	Rejected
230	[47]	Traceability of requirements in Agile Methodologies: A systematic mapping	2018	El Compendex	Rejected
231	[163]	Training students in evidence-based software engineering and systematic reviews: a systematic review and empirical study	2021	Springer Link	Rejected
232	[173]	Understanding How and When Human Factors Are Used in the Software Process: A Text-Mining Based Literature Review	2019	Springer Link	Accepted
233	[135]	Use of maximum lift and angle of attack, a review of experience within BAe military aircraft	1995	El Compendex	Rejected
234	[154]	User acceptance testing for Agile-developed web-based applications: Empowering customers through wikis and mind maps	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
235	[167]	User Stories and Natural Language Processing: A Systematic Literature Review	2021	El Compendex	Accepted
236	[73]	User story mapping: The hands-on course	2017	El Compendex	Rejected
237	[72]	User story mapping: The hands-on course	2016	El Compendex	Rejected
238	[187]	Using CMMI together with agile software development: A systematic review	2015	El Compendex	Rejected
239	[172]	Using concept maps to improve proactive information delivery in TaskNavigator	2010	El Compendex	Rejected
240	[17]	Using rules engine in the automation of system security review	2019	El Compendex	Rejected
241	[160]	Value stream mapping: Operationalizing lean manufacturing	2015	El Compendex	Rejected
242	[203]	Value stream maps and critical path method for production and procurement planning: A make to order company	2006	El Compendex	Rejected
243	[103]	A Qualitative Study on Non-Functional Requirements in Agile Software Development	2021	Manual	Accepted

Key	Family Solution	Solution	Type of Solution	Phase of RE	Considered Disruptive?
S1		A hierarchical requirements model	Model	Elicitation	No
S1		A requirements engineer who accompanies the on-site customer	Process	All	No
S1		Acceptance test-driven development (ATDD)	Technique	Specification	No
S1		Additional requirements documentation	All	Elicitation	No
S1		Aspect-oriented requirements approach	Approach	Management	No
S1	Story Board	Automatically validated against the storytests	Method	Validation	Yes
S1		Delivery stories, high level design and test scenarios	Technique	Specification	No
S1		Enhancing Scrum with goal-oriented requirements engineering and IT governance	Process	Conception/Design and Elicitation	No
S1		Ethnography	Method	Elicitation	No
S1		Explicit product and portfolio management processes	Process	Management	No
S1		Feature-driven development	Method	Validation/Verification	No
S1		Mind-mapping	Technique	Elicitation	No
S1		Roles such as the domain owner and business	Process	Analysis/Specification	No
S1		Test-driven development	Technique	Validation/Verification	No
S1		Traditional requirements analysis and specification process	Process	Analysis/Specification	No
S8		Analysis meetings (Planning Poker)	Technique	Analysis	No
S8		Backlog - Software requirements specification	Technique	Specification	No
S8		Brainstorming (points of view)	Technique	Elicitation	No
S8		Documentation (Burn-down and burn-up)	Technique	Management	No
S8		Interview	Technique	Elicitation	No
S8		Meeting	Technique	Elicitation	No
S8		Modeling	Technique	Elicitation	No
S8		On-site Observation	Technique	All	No
S8		Prioritization	Technique	Elicitation	No
S8		Prototypes (time-boxed)	Technique	Elicitation	No
S8		Reviews (Reviews Sprint)	Technique	Validation	No
S8		Scenarios	Technique	Specification	No
S8		Social analysis	Technique	Analysis	No
S8		Use cases (story uses)	Technique	Elicitation/Specification	No
S15		None	None		None
S7		Features tree model used to describe requirement and changes on requirement	Tool	Management	No
S7		Framework of requirements prioritization process used to get high quality requirement at time	Framework	Management	No
S7		Just in time approaches used to manage non-functional requirement	Approach	Management	No
S3		Checklist or definition of ready on requirements specifications	Process	Specification	No
S3		Use a list of quality criteria	Process	Specification	No
S3		Using tools that allow collaboration and traceability	Tool	Specification	No
S16		Agile methodologies	Approach	All	No
S16		Agile methodologies	Approach	All	No
S16	Bayesian Network	Bayesian network	Method	Management	Yes
S16	Scrum	ScrumLint	Tool	Management	Yes
S16	Continuous techniques	VCCTF (Version Control Continuous Testing Frame)	Framework	Validation	Yes
S17		Change Management	Practice	Management	No
S17		Code refactoring	Practice	Development	No
S17		Continuous planning	Approach	Management	No
S17		Cross-functional teams	Practice	Development	No
S17		Customer involvement and interaction (face-to-face communication)	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S17		Iterative requirements	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S17		Pairing for requirements analysis	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S17		Prototyping	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S17		Requirements management	Practice	Management	No
S17		Requirements modelling	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S17		Requirements prioritization	Practice	Management	No
S17		Retrospectives	Practice	Management; Validation	No
S17		Review meetings and acceptance tests	Practice	Development; Validation; Management	No
S17		Shared conceptualisations	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S17		Testing before coding	Practice	Development	No
S17		User stories	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S18		Acceptance criteria	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S18		Definition of Done	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S18		Traceability between FR and NFR	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S18		User stories	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S14		Agile security framework using a hybrid technique for requirements elicitation	Framework	Elicitation	No
S14		Dynamic Systems Development Method	Approach	Specification	No

Key	Family Solution	Solution	Type of Solution	Phase of RE	Considered Disruptive?
S14		Feature Driven Development	Approach	Specification	No
S14		Introducing new artifacts in ASD	Approach	Specification/Elicitation	No
S14		NORMATIC - tool for modeling NFR for agile processes.	Tool	Specification	No
S14		Security backlog	Approach	Specification/Elicitation	No
S14		Specific guidelines to be followed by stakeholders	Guidelines	Specification/Elicitation	No
S14		Vulnerability analyses	Approach	Specification/Elicitation	No
S19		Representation	Practice	Management	No
S19		Requirements change management (RCM)	Practice	Management	No
S19		use case model	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S20	Lean	Lean Startup	Approach	Management	Yes
S20	UCD	UCD - User Centered Design	Method	Development	Yes
S21	XP	XP - eXtreme Programming	Methods	Development	Yes
S22		Agile methodologies	Approach	All	No
S23		Change Management	Practice	Management	No
S23		Code refactoring	Practice	Development	No
S23		Continuous planning	Approach	Management	No
S23		Cross-functional teams	Practice	Development	No
S23		customer involvement and interaction	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S23		Face-to-face communication	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S23		Iterative requirements	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S23	Kanban	Kanban	Practice	Elicitation; Management	Yes
S23		Pairing for requirements analysis	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S23	Participatory Design	Participatory design activities	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S23	Persona	Persona	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S23		Prototyping	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S23	Test techniques	Quantitative Customer-driven (QCD)	Model	Elicitation; Validation	Yes
S23		Requirements management	Practice	Management	No
S23		Requirements modelling	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S23		Requirements prioritization	Practice	Management	No
S23		Retrospectives	Practice	Management; Validation	No
S23		Review meetings and acceptance tests	Practice	Development; Validation; Management	No
S23		RUP (Rational Unified Process)	Approach	All	No
S23		Scenario	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S23		Shared conceptualisation	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S23		Testing before coding	Practice	Development	No
S23		use case model	Practice	Elicitation; Design	No
S23		User stories	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S24		Agile methodologies	Approach	All	No
S9	Bayesian Network	Bayesian Network	Method	Management	Yes
S9		Change effort prediction	Method	Management	No
S9		COCOMO II	Method	Management	Yes
S9		Experience Factory	Method	Management	No
S9		Expert Judgment	Method	Management	No
S9		Function size Measurement	Method	Management	No
S9	Neural Network	Fuzzy Logic - Swarm Intelligence	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Decision tree, SVM, KNN, Ensemble-based method	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Document fingerprints	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Ensemble-based method	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - HKO Method	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - KNN	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Logistic Model Tree	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Naive bayes	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Random Forest	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Stochastic Gradient Bossting	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - SVM	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Machine Learning	Machine Learning - Text Classification	Method	Management	Yes
S9		Monte Carlo	Method	Management	No
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - ANN	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - ANN opitimized by Fireworks Algorithm	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - ANN with a Principal Component Step	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Deep belief network	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Deep belief network along with Antlion Optimization	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Elman	Method	Management	Yes

Key	Family Solution	Solution	Type of Solution	Phase of RE	Considered Disruptive?
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Evolutionary Cost-Sensitive Deep belief Network	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Feed foward	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Fuzzy Neural Network	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - General Regression Neural Network	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Independent Component Regression	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - KNN Regression	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Long deep recurrent Neural Network	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Neural Network	Neural Network - Multilayer Perceptrons	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Models	Ontology Model	Method	Management	Yes
S9		Planning Poker	Method	Management	No
S9		Principal component analysis	Method	Management	Yes
S9		Prioritization of Stories	Method	Management	No
S9		Regression	Method	Management	Yes
S9	Estimation tecniques	Statistical Combination	Method	Management	Yes
S9		Use case point	Method	Management	No
S9	Estimation tecniques	Wideband delphi	Method	Management	Yes
S25		Quality User Story (QUS)	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S25		User stories	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S26	Development techniques	Co-development with the user	Practice	All	Yes
S26	Continuous techniques	Continuous deployment	Approach	All	Yes
S26		Face-to-face communication	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S26	Participatory Design	Participatory design activities	Process	Elicitation	Yes
S26		Prototyping	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S4		Q-rapids - data-driven elicitation of quality requirements	Framework	Elicitation	No
S5		Expert judgment	Process	Management	No
S5		Face-to-face communication	Process	Elicitation; Management	No
S5		Iterative requirements	Process	Elicitation; Management	No
S5	Development techniques	Planning poker	Process	Management	Yes
S5		Prototyping	Process	Management	No
S5		Requirement modeling	Process	Management	No
S5		Requirement prioritization	Process	Management	No
S5		Retrospective	Process	Management	No
S5		Review meetings	Process	Management	No
S5		Story points	Process	Management	No
S5		Use Case Points (UCP)	Process	Management	No
S27		None	None		None
S28	Agile Methodologies	Adaptative Random Testing (ART)	Practice	Validation	Yes
S28	Goal Model	Goal Question Metric (GQM)	Practice	Validation	Yes
S28		Integration testing	Practice	Validation	No
S28		Regression testing	Practice	Validation	No
S28		Test case prioritization (TCP)	Practice	Validation	No
S28		Unified Modeling Language (UML)	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S29		Central Design Report (CDR)	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S29		Contextual Design	Practice	Elicitation; Design	No
S29		Contextual Inquiry	Practice	Elicitation; Design	No
S29		Continuous delivery	Approach	All	No
S29		Heuristic Evaluation	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S29	Estimation tecniques	Index cards	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S29	Persona	Persona	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S29		Prototyping	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S29		Scenario	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S29	Story Board	Story boarding	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S29		Usability testing	Practice	Validation	No
S29		User stories	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S29	Wizard of Oz	Wizard of Oz	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	Yes
S30	Canvas	Canvas	Practice	Management	Yes
S30	Design Thinking	Cognitive evolution	Practice	Elicitation	Yes
S30	Design Thinking	Design Thinking	Approach	All	Yes
S30	FDD	Feature-driven Development (FDD)	Approach	All	Yes
S30	Mind Mapping	Mind Mapping	Practice	Elicitation; Management	Yes
S30	Scrum	Scrum	Approach	All	Yes
S31	Bayesian Network	Bayesian network	Method	Management	Yes
S31	Design Thinking	Cognitive simulation	Method	Elicitation; Design	Yes

Key	Family Solution	Solution	Type of Solution	Phase of RE	Considered Disruptive?
S31	Agile Methodologies	Intelligent Software Engineering (ISE)	Practice	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S31	Machine Learning	Machine Learning	Process	All	Yes
S31	Natural Language Process	Natural Language	Method	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S31	Neural Network	Semantic network	Process	Elicitation; Design	Yes
S13		Jobs-To-Be-Done (JTBD) - Job Map	Framework	All	No
S6	Design Thinking	Design Thinking	Process	Elicitation	Yes
S6	Participatory Design	Participatory Design	Process	Elicitation	Yes
S6	Design Thinking	Service Design Thinking	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S6	UCD	UCD - User Centered Design	Method	Elicitation	Yes
S6	UCD	UCD - User Centered Design	Method	Elicitation	Yes
S32		None	None		None
S2		Architecture and requirements modeling	Technique	Specification	No
S33		Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)	Method	Management	Yes
S33		Automatic Runtime Reappraisal of Weights (ARROW)	Method	Management	Yes
S33	Natural Language Process	Non-Functional requirements model for Agile process (NORMAP)	Method	Management	Yes
S34		Continuous integration	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S34		Deliver story			No
S34		Face-to-face communication	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S34		Frequent prioritization	Practice	Management	No
S34		Iterative requirements	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S34		Pair programming	Practice	Development	No
S34		Product grooming			No
S34		Prototyping	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S34		Refactoring	Practice	Development	No
S34	TDD	Test-driven Development	Approach	All	Yes
S34		Unit testing	Practice	Validation	No
S34		User stories	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S34		Wiki	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S35	Agile Methodologies	Agile REST	Practice	Validation	Yes
S35	Agile Methodologies	Agile Software Testing (AST)	Practice	Validation	Yes
S35	Models	Model-based Testing (MBT)	Method	Validation	Yes
S35	TDD	Test-driven Development	Approach	All	Yes
S35		Unified Modeling Language (UML)	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S11		ACC	Technique	Specification	No
S11		ALC	Technique	Specification	No
S11		AUC	Technique	Specification	No
S11		BRAIMSTORMING	Technique	Elicitation	No
S11		Cucumber	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Diag. Ativo	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Doc. Requ.	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Feature	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Focal group	Technique	Elicitation	No
S11		GPM	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Interview	Technique	Elicitation	No
S11		INVEST	Technique	Specification	No
S11		JAD	Technique	Elicitation	No
S11		Mind Map	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Personas	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Questionnaire	Technique	Elicitation	No
S11		Scenarios	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Story Card	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Task	Technique	Specification	No
S11		TRAWLLING	Technique	Elicitation	No
S11		Use case	Technique	Specification	No
S11		User stories	Technique	Specification	No
S11		WALL	Technique	Specification	No
S11		Wireframe	Technique	Specification	No
S11		WORKSHOP	Technique	Elicitation	No
S11		XSBD	Technique	Specification	No
S11		XXM	Technique	Specification	No
S36	Agile Methodologies	Agile methodologies	Approach	All	Yes
S37		Change Management	Practice	Management	No
S37	XP	Code refactoring	Practice	Development	Yes

Key	Family Solution	Solution	Type of Solution	Phase of RE	Considered Disruptive?
S37		Continuous planning	Practice	Elicitation; Design	No
S37		Cross-functional teams	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S37		customer involvement and interaction			No
S37		Face-to-face communication	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S37		Iterative requirements	Practice	Elicitation; Management	No
S37	Development techniques	Pairing for requirements analysis			Yes
S37		Prototyping	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S37		Requirements management	Practice	Management	No
S37		Requirements prioritization	Practice	Management	No
S37		Retrospectives	Practice	Management	No
S37		Review meetings and acceptance tests	Practice	Management; Validation	No
S37		Shared conceptualisations			No
S37		Testing before coding	Practice	Elicitation; Validation	No
S37		User stories	Practice	Elicitation; Design; Validation	No
S38		None	None		None
S39		None	None		None
S40		Change Vector	Practice	Management	Yes
S40	Estimation tecniques	Cumulative Voting	Practice	Management	Yes
S40		Decision Knowledge	Practice	Management	No
S40		Flowchart Model	Practice	Management	No
S40	Goal Model	Goal Model	Practice	Management	Yes
S40		Numerical Assignment	Practice	Management	No
S40	Estimation tecniques	Planning poker	Practice	Management	Yes
S40		Weighted Sum	Practice	Management	No
S12		Agile Model-Driven Development - MDD- based.	Approache	All	No
S41		None	None		None
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Bag-of-words	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Clustering	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Dependency	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Fuzzy set theory	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Latent Dirichlet Allocation	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Lemmatization	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Logistic regression	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Machine learning	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Named-entity recognizer	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Open information extraction	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - POS tag	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Preprocessing	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Semantic role labeling	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Similarity matrix	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Skip-gram	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Syntactic parse tree	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Term frequency-inverse document frequency	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - Vector space model	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S10	Natural Language Process	NLP in users stories - WuP similarity	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
S42		Customer-developer meeting	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Interview with users/customer representatives	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Interview with technical experts	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Dedicated NFR elicitation workshops	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Mini-QAW (Quality Attribute Workshop)	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Requirements Elicitation workshops	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Brainstorming	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Prototyping	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Moderated circulation of NFRs document between Product Owner and NFR stakeholders	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Instantiation of patterns from NFR catalog	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		Using standards or other NFR classification sources as a reference	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		On the basis of a training provided to the customer in each iteration	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		On the basis of business process models	Technique	Elicitation	No
S42		By automated OCR and text processing of project documents and images	Technique	Elicitation	Yes
Total records			311		

Table 5. Family Solutions

Family Solution	Phases of RE and Studies	Quantity Solution
Agile Methodologies	Elicitation; Design (S31); Validation (S28 S35 S23); All (S36)	6
Bayesian Network	Management (S16 S9 S31)	5
Canvas	Management (S30)	1
Design Thinking	Elicitation (S30 S31 S6);	4
Development techniques	Management (S9 S5); All (S26)	3
Estimation techniques	Elicitation (S29); Management (S9 S40)	5
FDD	All (S30)	1
Goal Model	Management (S9 S40); Validation (S28)	3
Kanban	Management (S23)	1
Lean	Management (S20)	1
Machine Learning	Management (S9); All (S31)	12
Mind Mapping	Elicitation; Management (S30)	1
Natural Language Process	Elicitation (S31 S10); Management (S33)	22
Neural Network	Elicitation (S31); Management (S9)	16
Persona	Elicitation (S23 S29 S11)	3
Scrum	Management (S16 S30)	2
Story Board	Elicitation (S29); Validation (S1)	2
TDD	All (S34 S35)	2
Test techniques	Validation (S16)	1
UCD	Elicitation (S23 S26 S6); All (S20)	7
XP	All (S21 S26 S37)	5
Other	Elicitation (S29 S23); Management (S9 S33 S40); Validation (S29 S35)	3
Total		106

Table 6: Challenges for family solution

Family solution	Studies key	Challenges
Agile Methodologies	(S23) (S31) (S35) (S36)	Allocate resources and estimate time
		Automation of tests
		Combine agility and process control
		Communication between teams
		Control of the model-based tests
		Customer availability
		Customer inability and agreement
		Dependant on artificial intelligence
		Growing technical debt
		Inappropriate architecture
		Involve testers in requirements activities
		Lack of accuracy on estimations
		Lack of communication
		Lack of documentation
		Lack of knowledge
		Lack of team knowledge/ experience
		Manually accepted acceptance tests
Maturity of testing process		
Motivation issues		
Prioritization of test cases		
Design Thinking	(S6)	Reorganization of teams might be needed
		Training in novel techniques would be needed
		Users should be open-minded, willing to collaborate and patient
Development techniques	(S26) (S5)	Ability of the user to transfer knowledge
		Customer profile and behaviour
Estimation techniques	(S40)	Planning poker can have limitations in the case the estimation process is not well structured
		Difficulty to identify all requirements
		Difficulty to identify all requirements
		High Paid Person Opinion (HIPO) that restrict /change requirements
		Lack of customer involvement
Goal Model	(S28) (S40)	Market pressure
		Stakeholders conflicts
		Difficulty to identify all requirements
		High Paid Person Opinion (HIPO) that restrict /change requirements
		Lack of customer involvement
Natural Language Process	(S10)	Market pressure
		Non-experienced team can lead to a incorrect prioritization
		Stakeholders conflicts
		Cannot be generally uses in all contexts of the problem
		Complement rather than replace human decision making
		Compounds are difficult to identify correctly
		Conjunctions are also a challenge
Heterogeneity and low amount of data		
Persona	(S11)	Low precision
		Manual data tagging
		Not yet able to handle complex systems
		Verbs may be difficult to link to the proper object
		Absence of key people
UCD	(S6)	Communication gaps
		Conflicts when requirements come from multiple sources
		Constant reprioritization of requirements
		Difficulties in sustainable team practices
		Distributed teams
		Training in novel techniques would be needed
		Users should be open-minded, willing to collaborate and patient

Family solution	Studies key	Challenges
XP	(S21)	Ability to build applications from distributed locations
		Avalilability of experts
		Face-to-face communication
		Resource management
Other	(S40)	Transparency
		Difficulty to identify all requirements
		High Paid Person Opinion (HIPO) that restrict /change requirements
		Lack of customer involvement
		Market pressure
Stakeholders conflicts		

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